

EVALUATION OF A FIBER BUNDLE TWISTING AT A CURVED SECTION OF 3D PRINTED CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

H. Shiratori¹, A. Todoroki¹, M. Ueda², R. Matsuzaki³, Y. Hirano⁴

¹ Tokyo Institute of Technology, Meguro, Tokyo, Japan

² Nihon University, Chiyoda, Tokyo, Japan

³ Tokyo University of Science, Noda, Chiba, Japan

⁴ Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency, Mitaka, Tokyo, Japan

Keywords: Polymer Matrix Composite, 3D printing, CFRTP, Fiber twisting

ABSTRACT

The present study reveals the twisting mechanism of a continuous carbon fiber bundle in a curved section. In order to reveal this, the geometry of a printed fiber bundle and twisting process were observed. In addition, the finite element analysis was conducted to verify the twisting mechanism. As a result, the twisting of a fiber bundle is attributed to the difference between the direction and working point of adhesive force on the print bed and tensile force from the print nozzle. By measuring the electrical resistance of a fiber bundle, it was revealed that fibers are broken in a curved section. Twisting of a fiber bundle and fibers fracture can deteriorate the mechanical properties of the curved section of 3D printed composite materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

As carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) have superior mechanical properties and moldability the adaptation of this material has been expanding[1]. Recent technology enables us to fabricate CFRTP by 3D printing and the 3D printer can fabricate the complex geometry [2] and saving manufacturing cost by automizing its process. 3D printing enables to fabricate curved reinforcement fiber in composite materials. Curved fiber arrangement is very effective for optimizing structures and improving the freedom of design [3]. Matsuzaki et. al, revealed that in the 3D printing process of a continuous carbon fiber bundle, a fiber bundle is twisted in a curved section [4]. The mechanism of twisting and the effect of twisting have not been investigated, and the effect of the fiber twisting to the mechanical properties of CFRTP has not been revealed. To apply the 3D printed composite to structural components, revealing these issues are indispensable.

The objective of the present study is to clarify the mechanism of the twisting and the effect of twisting to the molding experimentally. The specimens with straight sections and curved sections have been printed and the difference of the geometry between each section have been tested. In addition, the twisting of a fiber bundle in the printing process has been observed to clarify the twisting mechanism. Finite element analysis (FEA) was performed to verify the twisting mechanism of a carbon fiber (CF) bundle.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

2.1 The geometry of the specimen.

The present study used CF bundles produced by MarkForged. A CF bundle consist of approximately a thousand carbon fibers and nylon. The specific data of the 3D printed object is shown in the reference. MarkTwo was used to print the specimens and Figure 1 shows the schematic geometry of the specimen. To investigate the effect of the radius at a curved section to the twisting of a fiber bundle, specimens were printed in the 4 different sets inner radius. ($r_{in} = 2, 5, 10, 15\text{mm}$).

2.2 Observation method for the geometry of the specimens and twisting process of a fiber bundle.

The surface observation was conducted using an optical microscope (Keyence, VH-5500). The sample for observing the cross section of a fiber bundle was prepared by cutting a printed fiber bundle at a straight section and twisting section after embedded the specimens into the resin. After cutting the sample, edge surface was polished before observing its cross-sections. The twisting process of a fiber bundle was observed by using the transparent acrylic print bed and set the mirror beneath it (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Observation of the twisting process of a fiber bundle.

2.3 Evaluation of the amount of fiber breakage at a curved section

Measurement of the electrical resistance of a fiber bundle was conducted by the 4-terminal method to testify the fiber breakage at a curved section. LCR meter (HIOKI, IM 3536) was used for this measurement. If the fiber breakage occurs at a curved section, the electrical resistance value per unit length at a curved section is speculated to be higher than that of the straight section. The amount of a fiber breakage at a curved section was calculated compared with the decreased rate of a cross section by fibers breakage, which is calculated using the equation (1).

$$R = \rho \frac{l}{S} \quad (1)$$

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

3.1 Observation result of surface and cross-section of a fiber bundle.

Figure 2 shows the surface images of fiber bundles. From these images, it is revealed that the smaller the curvature radius, the larger the twisting.

(a) $r_{in} = 2\text{mm}$

(b) $r_{in} = 10\text{mm}$

Figure 2 Surface images of printed CF bundles

Cross sections of the curved fiber bundles were observed. Table 1 shows the area of cross-section and calculated moment of inertia of area around the horizontal axis and vertical axis using Image J (NIH). From Table 1, flattening of a fiber bundle in a straight section was revealed because the moment of inertia of area of a straight section around the vertical axis is larger than that of around the horizontal axis. In addition, there was no big difference between the area of the cross-section of the straight section and the twisted section.

Axis direction	Straight section	Twisted section
Area of cross section mm ²	0.144	0.137
Horizontal I_x mm ⁴	1.03×10^{-3}	1.52×10^{-3}
Vertical I_y mm ⁴	4.18×10^{-3}	1.61×10^{-3}

Table 1 Area of cross-section and moment of inertia of area of a fiber bundle

3.2 Observation of the twisting process of a fiber bundle.

Observation of the printing process was conducted for revealing the twisting mechanism of a fiber bundle at a curved section. Figure 3 shows the printing process in a curved section. From Figure 3, because the width of a fiber bundle is smaller at a twisted section, the sections whose width of the bundle are narrow are presumably the twisted sections. This result shows that the twisting of a fiber bundle occurs in the printing process of a curved section. This may have been related to the difference of the direction of the tensile force from the print nozzle and adhesion force to the print bed.

Figure 3 Image of twisting of a fiber bundle

3.3 Measurement of the electrical resistance of a fiber bundle.

Figure 4 shows the relation between the inner curvature radius to the electrical resistance and the inner curvature radius to the rate of a breakage rate. From Figure 4, because the electrical resistance of a curved section was higher than that of a straight section, this result indicates the fiber breakage at a curved section. In addition, the curvature radius effects the fiber breakage. This is related to the fact that when twisting of a fiber bundle occurs, the fiber bundles are folded, thereby, the fiber bundle is scratched to the print nozzle.

Figure 4 Relation of electrical resistance and inner radius of a curved section

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 The mechanism of twisting of a fiber bundle in a curved section.

The mechanism of a fiber bundle twisting in a curved section is the following process. First, a fiber bundle is flattened by compressed between the print nozzle and print bed. This makes the fiber bundle deform easily to the thickness direction because the moment of inertia of area around the vertical axis becomes larger than that of the straight section. and Next, in the curved section, in order not to twist the fiber bundle, a longer fiber is necessary on the outside of the curved section. The length of fibers contained in a fiber bundle is considered to be the same, therefore, higher tensile load act on the outside of the curved section. In addition, the working point of the adhesive force and tensile load is displaced in the thickness direction, the twisting torque is generated. This twisting torque makes the fiber bundle twisting at a curved section as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Mechanism of folding a fiber bundle

4.2 Testifying the folding mechanism of a fiber bundle using finite elemental analysis

To testify the twisting mechanism of a fiber bundle, the finite elemental analysis was conducted using ANSYS Workbench 18.2. Figure 6 (a) shows the model for the analysis. This model expresses the geometry of a curved fiber. The tip of the model describes the geometry of a fiber bundle when it is extruded from the print nozzle. In order to express the adhesion to the print bed, displacement constraint was affected by the straight section of the analysis model. In addition, the tensile load was affected by

the tip of the model. The material properties used for this analysis is shown in Table 2. Figure 6 (b) shows the analysis result. From this result, it was revealed that the twisting of a fiber attributed to the positional relation between the tensile load from the print nozzle and tensile load from the print bed.

Figure 6 Finite elemental analysis

Material properties	Value
Longitudinal elastic modulus E_L GPa	120
Transverse elastic modulus E_T GPa	7.2
Out of plane elastic modulus E_Z GPa	7.2
In-plane shear modulus G_{LT} GPa	3.7
Out of plane shear modulus in longitudinal direction G_{LZ} GPa	3.7
Out of plane shear modulus in transverse direction G_{TZ} GPa	2.6
In-plane Poisson's ratio ν_{LT}	0.38
Out-of-plane Poisson's ration in longitudinal direction ν_{LZ}	0.38
Out-of-plane Poisson's ratio in transverse direction ν_{TZ}	0.38

Table 2 Material properties for FEM

9 CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, the twisting mechanism of a continuous carbon fiber bundle was clarified and amount of fibers breakage in a curved section was measured. As a result, the twisting of a fiber bundle attribute to the positional relation between a tensile load from the print nozzle and adhesion forces from the print bed. In addition, it was revealed that fibers breakage in a curved section, and it can deteriorate the strength of a curved section of 3D printed continuous fiber reinforced plastics.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Der Klift, Y.Koga, A.Todoroki, M.Ueda, Y.Hirano, R.Matsuzaki, 3D printing of continuous fiber reinforced thermos-plastic(CFRTP) tensile test specimens, *Open Journal of Composite Materials*, 6, 1, 2016, pp.18-27.

- [2] Y. Yamanaka, A. Todoroki, M. Ueda, Y. Hirano, R. Matsuzaki, Fiber line optimization in single ply for 3D printed composites, *Open Journal of Composite Materials*, 6, 4, 2016, pp. 121-131.
- [3] H. Zhang, D. Yang, Y. Sheng, Performance-driven 3D printing of continuous curved carbon fibre reinforced polymer composites: A preliminary numerical study, *Composite Part B*, 151, 2018, pp. 256-264.
- [4] R. Matsuzaki, T. Nakamura, K. Sugiyama, M. Ueda, A. Todoroki, Y. Hirano, Y. Yamagata, Effect of set curvature and fiber bundle size on the printed radius of curvature by a continuous carbon fiber composite 3D printer, *Additive Manufacturing*, 24, 2018, pp. 93-102.